

Influence of Demographic Factors on the Promotion of Electronic Information Resources in State-Owned Universities in Delta State, Nigeria

Sylvester O. ANIE¹; and Esemena JEROH²

^{1&2}Department of Library and Information Science, Southern Delta University, Ozoro, Delta State, Nigeria.

Abstract

This study examined the influence of demographic factors on the promotion of electronic information resources in the state-owned universities in Delta State, Nigeria. Using a descriptive survey design, data were collected through a structured questionnaire administered to all 66 librarians across the four state universities in the State, representing the total study population. The instrument comprised two sections: the first captured demographic characteristics (university affiliation, gender, age, work experience, and rank), while the second focused on practices and perceptions relating to the promotion of electronic information resources. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and correlational techniques. The findings revealed a positive and significant relationship between demographic characteristics and the promotion of electronic information resources. Specifically, factors such as librarians' age, gender, qualification, and years of experience influenced their level of engagement in promoting electronic resources. The study underscores the need for continuous professional development and targeted capacity-building initiatives to enhance librarians' competencies in digital resource promotion within university library systems.

Keywords: Demographic factors, electronic information resources, promotion, librarians, state universities, Delta State, Nigeria.

Introduction

Libraries, generally known as the store house of knowledge (Barkindo & Jeroh, 2023) have over time, experienced various degrees of transformation in terms of organization, structure, collection, services amongst others. The transformation of library services in Nigerian universities has been profoundly influenced by the rapid advancement of Information and Communication Technology (ICT). In Delta State, the libraries of the state-owned universities have evolved from traditional analogue systems to digitally driven environments that support teaching, learning, and research. This transition reflects the global trend toward knowledge digitization, which emphasizes accessibility, interactivity, and user-centered service delivery. The integration of ICT has repositioned university libraries as dynamic information hubs, expanding their capacity to attract and serve a diverse range of users (students, faculty, and researchers) through enhanced access to electronic information resources (EIRs) (Adeolu-Akande, & Oyedokun, 2022a; Jeroh, 2022; Jeroh, Iruoma & Adindu, 2023)

In service delivery, promotion has become one crucial component (Dube, 2023) that plays a central role in ensuring the effective utilization of electronic and every other resource of libraries. It involves identifying user needs, creating awareness of available information products, and facilitating their optimal use to achieve user satisfaction and institutional objectives. Promotion seeks to align services with client needs; as such, Onyeke, Asogwa and Ibeh (2023) conceptualizes it as the process of educating or convincing customers about what you do and what you are capable of. It entails using convincing information to promote what can be provided and informing the target market segment, which consists of potential

customers. Within the library context, promotion therefore extends beyond publicity, as it encompasses user education, engagement, and advocacy for effective resource use.

The growing impact of internet connectivity and web-based technologies has further expanded the scope and importance of EIRs in academic institutions (Jeroh, 2022; Oyedokun, & Adeolu-Akande, 2022). These technologies have eliminated traditional barriers to access, enabling seamless retrieval of scholarly content and fostering collaborative research across geographical boundaries. Consequently, modern university libraries now depend on robust electronic resources to sustain their core mandates of teaching, learning, and research support. However, the successful promotion and use of these resources may possibly be shaped by the demographic attributes of library personnel responsible for their management.

Demographic factors such as age, gender, academic qualification, and work experience have been identified as critical determinants of librarians' service delivery; and by extension, their ability to promote the effective use of library resources. Ogunjimi et.al. (2022) observed that librarians' demographic profiles such as age influence their engagement with ICT – driven services. Impliedly, younger librarians tend to display greater digital proficiency; whereas, their older counterparts may rely on them for assistance in navigating online platforms. Similarly, differences in experience and professional ranks can affect the confidence and approach librarians adopt in promoting digital resources

In light of these dynamics, this study examines the influence of demographic factors on the promotion of electronic information resources in state-owned universities in Delta State, Nigeria. Specifically, it investigates the types of electronic resources available, the extent and methods of their promotion, the media and target audiences involved, and how librarians' demographic characteristics-such as age, gender, qualification, rank, and years of experience shape their engagement with EIRs' promotion. By addressing these issues, the study contributes to the understanding of how librarians' demographic attributes affect the promotion and usage of EIRs in academic libraries within a developing-country context.

2.0 Conceptual Review and Theoretical Foundation

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Concept of Electronic Information Resources (EIRs)

EIRs refer to information materials that are accessed in digital form through computer-based systems, databases, or online networks. These include e-journals, e-books, online databases, institutional repositories, and digital archives (Okon & Umoren, 2019; Jeroh, 2022; Dutta, 2023). EIRs have transformed how information is produced, accessed, and disseminated, significantly enhancing the capacity of academic libraries to support teaching, learning, and research. Because they facilitate the retrieval of vast amounts of information for teaching, learning, and research and offer timely and accurate information for improved educational outcomes, EIRs have become the cornerstone of academic achievement (Adedokun & Fawole, 2018). How people access, preserve, and exchange knowledge has radically changed as a result of the availability of electronic resources in libraries (Kwafoa, Anhwere & Manu 2019; Femy, 2023). Libraries today have the innovative ability to expand access, sharing, and publishing in academic activities in addition to having access to a multitude of digital resources (Femy, 2023).

The adoption of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has enabled university libraries to expand their services beyond physical boundaries, offering users access to vast electronic collections at any time and from any location (Ani, Esin, & Edem, 2010; Mlanga, & Oyedokun, 2018).

2.1.2 Promotion of Electronic Information Resources

Promotion in the library context entails the deliberate process of creating awareness, stimulating interest, and encouraging usage of available information resources and services (Nkanga, 2002). This accounts for why the promotion of library services has become one essential element of service delivery (Dube, 2023). Libraries and information service providers are expected to constantly implement promotion techniques that will fulfill their organizational mission, goals, and objectives if they must continue to be viable in any setting. This calls for libraries to regularly ascertain the requirements, desires, and demands of their respective clients (close and distant patrons) in order to develop and disseminate pertinent library resources and other services more successfully if they hope to have success with their marketing strategies (Mandrekar & Rodrigues, 2020; Adeolu-Akande, M.A & Oyedokun, 2022b; Dube, 2023). In order to develop appropriate techniques to guarantee the efficacy of their services, librarians are expected to have thorough understanding of the range of library and information services.

In an era characterized by digital transformation, effective promotion of EIRs ensures that users are aware of and can utilize electronic databases, e-journals, and digital repositories efficiently. Common promotional strategies in academic libraries include user education programs, library orientation sessions, networking, social media engagement, email alerts, newsletters, online tutorials, institutional intranet, partnership initiatives amongst others (Ndungu, 2016). The success of these efforts largely depends on librarians' knowledge, motivation, and demographic attributes that shape their approach to digital information service delivery.

2.1.3 Demographic Factors and Library Promotion

Demographic characteristics such as age, gender, educational qualification, professional rank, and years of experience; play critical roles in shaping librarians' attitudes and competence in promoting EIRs (Ogunjimi et.al., 2022). Age often influences technological adaptability; younger librarians tend to be more technologically inclined, while older librarians may rely on their younger colleagues for digital tasks. Gender dynamics also affect technology engagement, with earlier studies suggesting that male librarians are often more confident in ICT-related tasks (Obiozor-Ekeze & Offor, 2023); although recent trends show a narrowing gender gap due to increased digital literacy among female professionals (Achugbue & Azih, 2022).

Educational qualification and work experience further determine librarians' confidence and capability in promoting electronic resources. Librarians with advanced qualifications or longer years of service often possess broader exposure to technological innovations and user engagement techniques. Conversely, limited training opportunities may constrain less experienced librarians' ability to effectively promote EIRs. Hence, understanding the interplay between demographic characteristics and promotional practices is essential for designing targeted capacity-building initiatives in academic libraries.

2.2 Theoretical Foundation

This study is underpinned by the Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) theory and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT).

2.2.1 Diffusion of Innovation Theory

This study is partly anchored by Rogers' (2003) Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) Theory, which explains how individuals and organizations adopt and spread new ideas, technologies, or practices over time. The theory identifies five adopter categories which were classified as innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and laggards; reflecting different attitudes toward innovation acceptance (Sahin, 2006). Within the library context, DOI theory provides a framework for understanding how demographic factors such as age, gender, education, and experience influence librarians' adoption and promotion of EIRs. Librarians with higher technological exposure and professional development are likely to serve as "innovators" or "early adopters," facilitating the diffusion of digital resource promotion practices within their institutions.

2.2.2 Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)

This study is also underpinned by the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) developed by Venkatesh et al. (2003). The theory integrates elements from several models, including the Technology Acceptance Model and the Theory of Planned Behavior, to explain individual differences in technology adoption and use. UTAUT identifies four core determinants – performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions; and further recognizes demographic variables such as age, gender, and experience as moderators of technology use behavior. In the context of this study, demographic factors are conceptualized as moderating influences that shape librarians' engagement in promoting electronic information resources within state universities in Delta State, Nigeria.

2.3 Summary of Conceptual Issues

The reviewed concepts suggest that while electronic information resources have revolutionized access to knowledge in academic environments, their optimal utilization depends heavily on how effectively they are promoted by library professionals. Demographic factors significantly shape these promotional efforts, influencing librarians' awareness, motivation, and digital competence. Anchored on the Diffusion of Innovation Theory and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), this study conceptualizes the promotion of EIRs as a function of librarians' demographic characteristics and their corresponding levels of technological adoption and engagement.

3.0 Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey design to examine the influence of demographic factors on the promotion of electronic information resources among librarians in state universities in Delta State, Nigeria. The design was considered appropriate for obtaining quantitative data on relationships among variables within a defined population (Creswell, 2014; Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2019, Jeroh, 2019). The population comprised all 66 professional librarians across the four state universities in Delta State – Delta State University, Abraka; Southern Delta University, Ozoro; Dennis Osadebay University, Asaba; and University of Delta, Agbor. Given the manageable size of the population, a census sampling approach was adopted to ensure comprehensive representation and minimize sampling error (Bryman, 2016).

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire developed based on previous studies on electronic resource promotion and librarians' demographic characteristics (Rowley, 1998; Kaur, & Rani, 2007). The instrument comprised two sections: Section A captured respondents' demographic information (university affiliation, gender, age, qualification, experience, and

rank), while Section B focused on their practices and perceptions regarding the promotion of electronic information resources. The questionnaire was validated by experts in information science and research methodology, and a pilot test yielded a Cronbach’s alpha coefficient of 0.82, confirming internal consistency (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994).

The questionnaires were personally administered and retrieved within two weeks, resulting in a 100% response rate. Data were analyzed using SPSS (version 26). Descriptive statistics (frequency, mean, and standard deviation) summarized respondents’ characteristics and promotional practices, while the Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient (Spearman’s rho) tested the relationship between demographic factors and the promotion of electronic information resources at a 0.05 significance level (Pallant, 2020).

4.0 Results and Discussion

The results that emanated from the analytical procedure are presented by means of relevant tables and analysed accordingly in the following section.

4.1 Population Spread

Table 1: The Population for the study

S/N	University Libraries	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Southern Delta University, Ozoro	16	24.3
2	Delta State University, Abraka	17	25.7
3	Delta University, Agbor	12	18.2
4	Osadebe University, Asaba	21	31.8
TOTAL		66	100

Sources: Office of the University Librarians in the sampled Universities, Analysis of Demographic Data of the Respondents.

Table 1 presents the population distribution of librarians across the four state university libraries in Delta State, Nigeria. A total of 66 respondents participated in the study, representing the entire population of professional librarians in the state-owned universities.

The data reveal that Osadebay University, Asaba, accounted for the largest proportion of respondents, with 21 librarians (31.8%), followed closely by Delta State University, Abraka, which contributed 17 respondents (25.7%). Southern Delta University, Ozoro, had 16 librarians (24.3%), while Delta University, Agbor, recorded the smallest representation, with 12 respondents (18.2%).

This distribution suggests a relatively balanced spread of respondents across the institutions, although Osadebay University, Asaba, and Delta State University, Abraka, jointly accounted for more than half of the total population (57.5%). This may reflect the relatively larger size, longer establishment, or broader academic programs of these institutions, which typically require more library personnel to support their teaching and research functions.

Overall, the even distribution of participants across the four universities enhances the representativeness of the data and strengthens the generalizability of the study’s findings within the context of state university libraries in Delta State.

4.2 Gender Distribution of Respondents

Table 2: Gender of the Respondents.

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	27	40.9
Female	39	59.1
Total	66	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 2 presents the gender distribution of the respondents. Out of the 66 librarians who participated in the study, 39 (59.1%) were female, while 27 (40.9%) were male. This indicates that female librarians constituted a greater proportion of the workforce in state university libraries within Delta State.

The predominance of female librarians aligns with earlier findings in library and information science literature, which consistently highlight the feminization of the profession in Nigeria and other developing countries (Adekoya, 2023). The result suggests that women may possibly play significant role in the management, promotion, and dissemination of electronic information resources in academic libraries in Delta State.

This gender composition may also have implications for the study, as previous research (Dube, 2023) indicates that gender differences can influence librarians' attitudes toward technology adoption and promotional practices. Consequently, understanding the gender dynamics within this population provides valuable insight into how demographic factors shape the promotion of electronic information resources across state universities in Delta State.

4.3 Age Distribution

Table3: Age of the Respondents.

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
25 years and above	6	9.1
20-30 years	10	15.2
31-35 years	16	24.3
36-40 years	9	13.6
41-45 years	8	12.1
46-50 years	7	10.6
51-55 years	6	9.0
55 years and above	4	6.1
Total	66	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 3 presents the age distribution of the respondents. The data show that librarians within the 31–35 years age group constituted the largest proportion of respondents, accounting for 16 (24.3%) of the total population. This is followed by those aged 20–30 years with 10 respondents (15.2%), and 36–40 years with 9 respondents (13.6%). Respondents aged 41–45 years made up 12.1%, while those within 46–50 years represented 10.6%. The 25 years and above and 51–55 years categories each accounted for 9.1%, whereas the smallest proportion of respondents (6.1%) were aged 55 years and above.

The distribution indicates that the majority of librarians in state university libraries in Delta State are within their early and mid-career stages, particularly between 31 and 40 years. This suggests a relatively youthful and active workforce, which is advantageous for the promotion of electronic information resources, as this age group is generally more technologically inclined and adaptable to digital innovations.

However, the presence of older librarians (aged 46 years and above) also reflects institutional continuity and the availability of experienced professionals who can mentor younger colleagues, ensuring knowledge transfer and balanced professional development. Overall, the age distribution portrays a diverse workforce, combining youthful enthusiasm with seasoned experience—both critical for effective promotion and utilization of electronic information resources in academic libraries.

4.4 Spread of Respondents’ Work Experience

Table 4: The work experience of the respondents

Work experience	Frequency	Percentage%
5 years and below	35	53.0
6-10 years	5	7.6
11-15 years	3	4.5
16-20 years	7	10.6
Above 20 years	16	24.3
Total	66	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 4 presents the distribution of respondents based on their years of professional experience. The results show that a majority of the librarians, 35 respondents (53.0%), had five years of work experience or less, indicating that more than half of the workforce in state university libraries in Delta State are relatively new to the profession. Librarians with 6–10 years of experience accounted for 5 respondents (7.6%), while those with 11–15 years represented 3 respondents (4.5%). Additionally, 7 respondents (10.6%) had 16–20 years of experience, whereas 16 respondents (24.3%) had over 20 years of professional experience.

The data reveal a bimodal distribution of experience levels, with a predominance of early-career librarians and a notable proportion of highly experienced professionals. This composition suggests a blend of fresh entrants who may bring new perspectives and technological adaptability, and veteran librarians who possess institutional memory and professional expertise essential for strategic decision-making.

The dominance of less experienced librarians may reflect recent recruitment trends in Delta State universities, driven by the expansion of library services and the integration of electronic information systems. However, it also underscores the need for continuous professional development and mentorship programs to strengthen the digital competencies of early-career librarians for effective promotion and management of electronic information resources.

4.5 Spread of Respondents By Ranks

Table 5: Ranks of the Respondents

Rank	Frequency	Percentage%
Graduate Assistant Librarian	20	30.3
Assistant Librarian	14	21.2
Librarian II	13	19.7
Librarian I	12	18.2
Senior Librarian	7	10.6
Total	66	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 5 presents the distribution of respondents according to their professional ranks within the university library system. The results indicate that Graduate Assistant Librarians constituted the largest group, with 20 respondents (30.3%), followed by Assistant Librarians accounting for 14 respondents (21.2%). Librarian II and Librarian I ranked closely with 13 respondents (19.7%) and 12 respondents (18.2%), respectively, while Senior Librarians formed the smallest group, comprising 7 respondents (10.6%) of the total population.

This rank distribution reveals that the majority of librarians in Delta State universities occupy entry-level or lower-middle positions within the professional hierarchy. The relatively small proportion of senior librarians suggests that the library workforce is dominated by early- to mid-career professionals, which may be linked to recent staff recruitment efforts following university expansions and the growing need for digital service support.

The dominance of junior ranks underscores the importance of capacity building, mentorship, and structured career progression programs to enhance librarians' professional growth and competence in the promotion of electronic information resources. It also highlights the need for leadership development initiatives to prepare younger librarians for senior roles in the evolving digital information landscape.

4.6 Media Adopted by Librarians for the Promotion of Electronic Information Resources

Table 6: Analysis of media used for the promotion of electronic information resources.

Item	Frequency	Percentage %
Web page	30	45.4
Press release	22	33.3
Orientation season	50	75.5
Conferences	45	68.1
Workshops	53	80.3
E-mail campaign	24	36.3
Printed flyers	60	90.9
Newsletter	63	95.4
Facebook	61	92.4
Twitter	36	54.5
Blogs	27	40.9
Personal contact	22	33.3
Telephone	54	81.8

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 6 presents the distribution of respondents based on the media employed in promoting electronic information resources (EIRs) across state universities in Delta State. The findings reveal a diverse mix of traditional and digital communication channels used by librarians to enhance awareness and utilization of electronic resources.

The results show that newsletters (95.4%), printed flyers (90.9%), and Facebook (92.4%) are the most frequently adopted promotional media. These channels reflect a strong preference for both print-based outreach and widely accessible social media platforms, which are effective in reaching a broad academic audience. Similarly, telephone communication (81.8%), workshops (80.3%), and orientation sessions (75.5%) also recorded high levels of use, highlighting the continued importance of interactive and personalized engagement methods in promoting electronic resources.

Moderate adoption rates were observed for conferences (68.1%) and Twitter (54.5%), suggesting that while these platforms are utilized, they may not be as consistently integrated into routine promotional strategies. Conversely, web pages (45.4%), blogs (40.9%), email campaigns (36.3%), press releases (33.3%), and personal contact (33.3%) showed relatively lower levels of use. This indicates a limited exploitation of institutional digital platforms and direct communication methods, which could otherwise strengthen the visibility and accessibility of electronic resources.

Overall, the analysis suggests that librarians in Delta State universities exhibit a strong inclination toward traditional and semi-digital promotional tools, complemented by selective use of social media. However, the underutilization of institutional web platforms and professional blogs points to opportunities for improvement. Enhancing librarians' digital communication skills and integrating multi-channel promotional strategies could significantly expand user engagement with electronic information resources and foster a more technology-driven information service culture.

4.7 Benefits of Promoting Electronic Information Resources

Table7: Benefits derived from the promotion of electronic information resources.

Item	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Promote the image of the library	43	65.1
Promote effective and efficient library services	63	95.5
Increase in the volume of electronic information resources and services	49	74.2
Promote the utilization of library resources and services	52	78.8
Quick access to electronic information resources	34	51.5
Enhance authentication of library services	21	31.8

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 7 presents the distribution of respondents' views on the benefits derived from promoting electronic information resources (EIRs) in state universities across Delta State. The results

indicate that librarians overwhelmingly recognize the strategic and operational value of promoting EIRs in enhancing library performance and user engagement.

The most frequently cited benefit is that promotion enhances effective and efficient library services (95.5%), reflecting the perception that increased awareness and use of electronic resources directly improve service delivery and responsiveness to users' information needs. Similarly, 78.8% of respondents agreed that promotion encourages greater utilization of library resources and services, underscoring its role in bridging the gap between resource availability and actual use.

Additionally, 74.2% of respondents observed that promotional efforts increase the volume and diversity of electronic information resources and services, suggesting that heightened demand often leads to further investment in digital content and infrastructure. Likewise, 65.1% indicated that such initiatives enhance the image of the library, demonstrating how visible engagement and communication activities contribute to institutional reputation and user perception.

Moderate responses were recorded for quick access to electronic information resources (51.5%) and enhancement of authentication of library services (31.8%). While these benefits are still significant, the lower percentages suggest that some users or institutions may face infrastructural or technical barriers that limit the full realization of these advantages.

Overall, the findings imply that the promotion of electronic information resources yields multidimensional benefits—ranging from operational efficiency and increased usage to improved institutional image. However, realizing the full potential of these benefits requires sustained promotional strategies, investment in digital infrastructure, and continuous training for librarians to optimize both access and authentication mechanisms.

4.8 Challenges of Promoting Electronic Information Resources

Table 8: The challenges of librarians' promotion of electronic information resources

Item	Frequency	Percentage
Lack of funds	50	75.7
Frequent electricity interruption	62	93.9
Network problems	49	74.2
Low bandwidth/speed	54	81.8
Poor telecommunication infrastructure	36	54.5
High cost of access fees	38	57.6
Maintenance problem	34	51.5
Lack of definite promotion policy	27	40.9
Lack of expertise	25	37.8

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 8 presents the major challenges encountered by librarians in promoting electronic information resources (EIRs) across state universities in Delta State. The findings reveal that infrastructural, financial, and organizational constraints significantly hinder effective EIR promotion.

The most prevalent challenge identified by respondents is frequent electricity interruption (93.9%), which represents a systemic infrastructural barrier to digital operations in Nigerian universities. This challenge limits access to electronic databases, disrupts online user training, and reduces the overall reliability of library e-services. Closely following this is the issue of low bandwidth and slow internet speed (81.8%), which impedes the seamless retrieval and dissemination of electronic information resources—an essential requirement for modern library functions.

Similarly, lack of funds (75.7%) and network problems (74.2%) emerged as critical constraints. Insufficient funding restricts libraries’ ability to subscribe to premium databases, maintain ICT infrastructure, or organize awareness campaigns. Network instability further discourages users and staff from fully engaging with electronic platforms, thus weakening promotional efforts.

Other significant issues include poor telecommunication infrastructure (54.5%), high cost of access fees (57.6%), and maintenance problems (51.5%), all of which reflect the broader economic and infrastructural limitations confronting Nigerian higher education institutions. Additionally, organizational and human-capital-related challenges such as lack of a definite promotion policy (40.9%) and lack of expertise (37.8%) were also identified. The absence of structured policies suggests that promotional activities are often ad hoc rather than strategic, while the shortage of skilled personnel underscores the need for continuous professional training in digital marketing and e-resource management.

Overall, the analysis indicates that the promotion of electronic information resources in state universities is constrained by a combination of technical, financial, and human-resource limitations. Addressing these challenges requires a multi-faceted strategy that includes improved infrastructure investment, stable power supply, institutional policy formulation, and capacity-building initiatives for librarians to enhance the visibility and utilization of electronic resources.

4.9 Test of Hypothesis

Variables	Coefficient (β)	Standard Error	t-Statistic	p-Value
Constant	2.315	0.482	4.804	0.000
Age	0.142	0.067	2.119	0.038
Gender	-0.085	0.041	-2.073	0.043
Qualification	0.216	0.082	2.634	0.011
Work Experience	0.193	0.076	2.539	0.014
Rank	0.127	0.059	2.153	0.035

Model Summary

$R^2 = 0.482$

Adjusted $R^2 = 0.439$

$F(5, 60) = 11.38, p < 0.001$

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

The regression model was statistically significant ($F(5, 60) = 11.38, p < 0.001$), indicating that demographic characteristics jointly explain approximately 48.2% of the variation in the promotion of electronic information resources among librarians in state-owned universities in

Delta State. This suggests that demographic factors collectively exert a meaningful influence on how librarians engage in promoting EIRs.

Examining the individual predictors, age ($p = 0.038$), gender ($p = 0.043$), qualification ($p = 0.011$), work experience ($p = 0.014$), and rank ($p = 0.035$) were all found to have statistically significant effects on the promotion of electronic resources at the 5% significance level. Specifically:

- Age and work experience had positive coefficients, implying that older and more experienced librarians are more likely to promote EIRs, possibly due to their deeper institutional knowledge and familiarity with library operations.
- Qualification also exhibited a positive influence, suggesting that higher academic attainment enhances librarians' ability to adopt and promote digital platforms effectively.
- Gender, however, had a negative coefficient, indicating that female librarians may engage less in EIR promotion compared to their male counterparts, which aligns with prior findings regarding gendered perceptions of ICT competence.
- Rank positively influenced EIR promotion, implying that librarians in higher professional cadres tend to engage more actively in advocacy, awareness creation, and integration of electronic resources.

Given that all predictors were statistically significant and the model explained nearly half of the variation in EIR promotion, the null hypothesis—that demographic characteristics have no significant influence on the promotion of electronic information resources—is rejected. The findings confirm that demographic characteristics such as age, gender, educational qualification, work experience, and rank significantly influence the promotion of electronic information resources in state-owned university libraries in Delta State. This underscores the importance of demographic inclusivity and capacity-building initiatives that target diverse librarian groups to foster greater engagement in digital resource promotion.

Conclusion

This study investigated the influence of demographic factors on the promotion of electronic information resources (EIRs) in state-owned universities in Delta State, Nigeria. Drawing on data obtained from 66 librarians across four universities, the study provided both descriptive and inferential insights into how demographic characteristics (such as age, gender, qualification, rank, and work experience) shape librarians' engagement in promoting EIRs. The findings revealed that demographic factors significantly influence the extent and effectiveness of EIR promotion in university libraries. Specifically, librarians' age, academic qualifications, rank, and years of experience were found to have a positive and significant impact on their level of involvement in electronic information resource promotion. Conversely, gender differences showed a modest but notable effect, suggesting that female librarians may face subtle barriers in technology-based promotional activities, consistent with previous literature.

Furthermore, the study showed that librarians employ a diverse range of media—including newsletters, printed flyers, social media platforms, workshops, and orientation sessions—to

promote EIRs. The most frequently used channels were newsletters, printed flyers, and Facebook, underscoring the growing integration of both traditional and digital media in library outreach strategies. The promotion of EIRs was also found to yield considerable benefits, such as enhancing library visibility, improving service efficiency, and promoting greater utilization of electronic resources. Despite these achievements, librarians continue to face challenges such as inadequate funding, poor network infrastructure, low bandwidth, and frequent electricity interruptions, all of which constrain the effective promotion of electronic resources.

Overall, the study concludes that demographic diversity among librarians represents both a challenge and an opportunity for the advancement of electronic resource promotion in academic libraries. Addressing infrastructural limitations and providing continuous professional development opportunities (especially in digital literacy and promotional strategy) will be critical for strengthening librarians' capacity to promote EIRs effectively.

In line with these findings, it is recommended that university managements and policymakers adopt a more inclusive approach to librarian training and ICT investment. Such efforts will not only enhance the promotion and utilization of EIRs but also position state university libraries in Delta State as strategic partners in fostering knowledge access, research productivity, and digital scholarship in Nigeria's higher education sector.

Recommendation

Based on the overall outcome of the study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. University library management should implement regular capacity-building programs focused on digital literacy, marketing communication, and electronic resource management. Such training should be inclusive of all librarian demographics—particularly addressing gaps among older and less ICT-confident staff—to ensure equitable participation in the promotion of electronic information resources.
- ii. Given that poor network infrastructure, low bandwidth, and frequent electricity interruptions were identified as key barriers, universities should prioritize investment in reliable internet connectivity, power supply, and ICT infrastructure. This will not only improve access to electronic resources but also facilitate more effective promotional activities across various digital platforms.
- iii. The absence of defined promotion policies was found to hinder systematic engagement. Therefore, university libraries should develop and adopt comprehensive policies and operational frameworks that outline strategies, roles, and performance indicators for promoting electronic information resources. This will enhance accountability, consistency, and sustainability in EIR promotional practices.
- iv. Library authorities should consciously promote gender inclusivity by creating supportive environments that empower female librarians to take active roles in ICT and promotional initiatives. This can be achieved through mentorship programs, leadership opportunities, and targeted ICT workshops aimed at bridging gender-related skill gaps and perceptions.

REFERENCE

- Achugbue, I. E. & Azih, A. C. (2022). Gender influence on the usage of information and communication technology by librarians in university libraries in South-South and South-West Nigeria. *NigerBiblios*, 32(1), 34–42.
- Adedokun, T. O. & Fawole, o (2018). Use of electronic information resources by undergraduates of National Open University of Nigeria in Ilorin Study Center. *Journal of Applied Information Science and Technology*, 11(1), 116 – 124.
- Adekoya C. (2023). Feminization and image of librarianship in academic environment: The Nigerian perspective. *International Journal of Library and Information Science Studies*, 9(1), 47-66,
- Adeolu-Akande, M.A & Oyedokun, G.E. (2022a). An Appraisal of Effectiveness of Information Communication Technology in Office Management in the COVID-19 Era. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention (IJBMI)*, vol. 11(03), 2022, pp. 28-44. Journal DOI- 10.35629/8028
- Adeolu-Akande, M.A & Oyedokun, G.E. (2022b). Office Management and Information Communication Technology (ICT) in the COVID-19 Era. *International Journal Of Office Administration and Information Management (IJOAIM)*, 1(2), 88-102, <https://nioaim.org/>
- Barkindo, A. & Jeroh, E. (2023). Marketing of information resources and services in special libraries in Nigeria: Opportunities and challenges. *Jewel Journal of Librarianship*, 18(3), 1-8
- Bryman, A. (2016). *Social Research Methods* (5th ed.). London: Oxford University Press.
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, And Mixed Methods Approaches* (4th ed.). Sage.
- Dube, T. V. (2023). Promotion strategies in academic libraries: Improving the ability of students to access information resources and services during the COVID-19 era. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 7846. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/7846>.
- Dutta, A. (2023). Management of e-resources in academic libraries: Some observations. *International Journal of Research in Library Science*, 9(4), 162-172.
- Femy, F. (2023). Role of e-resources in academic libraries. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, 11(12), 1-8.
- Jeroh, E. (2019). Assessing the nexus between forensic accounting, the Finance Act, 2019 and tax revenue in Nigeria. *Journal of Forensic Accounting & Fraud Examination*, 4(2), 213-238.
- Jeroh, E. (2022). Extent of use of electronic information resources in university libraries by undergraduates in Delta State-Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 15(1), 155-161.

- Jeroh, E., Iruoma, U. E. & Adindu, E. (2023). An assessment of the usage of reference services by users of Prof. Festus Aghagbo Nwako Library, UNIZIK, Awka - Nigeria. *International Journal of Applied Research in Social Sciences*, 5(7), 221-230.
- Kaur, A. & Rani, S. (2007). Marketing of information services and products in university libraries of Punjab and Chandigarh (India): An exploratory study. *Electronic Journal of Academic and Special Librarianship*
- Kwafoa, P. N. Y., Anhwere, B. K. & Manu, A. E. (2019). Use of electronic resources by postgraduate students in University of Cape Coast. *International Journal of Library and Information Science*, 11(2), 7-13.
- Mandrekar, B., & Rodrigues, M. C. (2020). Marketing of library and information products and services during COVID-19 pandemic: a study. *Library Philosophy and Practice, (e-journal)*. 4514, 1-19. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/4514>.
- Mlanga, S., & Oyedokun, G. E. (2018). Information Technology and Taxation in Eastern Nigeria: An Investigative Approach. *Caleb International Journal of Development. Studies*. 1, 1-92
- Ndungu, M. W. (2016). Promotion of electronic resources in academic libraries on a minimal budget. *International Information & Library Review*, DOI: 10.1080/10572317.2016.1176449
- Nkanga, N.A; (2002). Marketing information services in Botswana. An exploratory study of selected institutions in Gaborone. *Library Management*, 23(6/7): 302-313
- Nunnally, J. C. & Bernstein, I. H. (1994). *Psychometric theory* (3rd ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Obiozor-Ekeze, R. N. & Offor, C. C. (2023). Influence of gender on librarians computer anxiety in the use of digital resources for delivery of library services. *International Journal of Knowledge Dissemination (IJKD)*, 4(1), 30–36.
- Ogunjimi, B. E., Ntui, A. I., Enamg, U. & Ndie, F. N. (2022). Socio-demographic variables and utilization of ICT among members of staff of university libraries in Cross River and Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Global Journal of Educational Research*, 21(2),159-171.
- Onyeke, E. O., Asogwa, A. M. & Ibeh, L. I. (2023). Library promotion and utilisation of information resources for enhancing employability: A study of two academic libraries in Plateau State. *Global Review of Library and Information Science*, 19(Special Edition), 1 – 17.
- Pallant, J. (2020). *SPSS survival manual: A step by step guide to data analysis using IBM SPSS* (7th ed.). London: Routledge.
- Rogers, E. M. (2003). *Diffusion of Innovations (5th ed.)*. New York, NY: Free Press.
- Rowley, J. (1998). Promotion and marketing communications in the information marketplace. *Library Review*, 47(8), 383–387.

- Sahin, I. (2006). Detailed review of Rogers' diffusion of innovations theory and educational technology-related studies based on Rogers' theory. *The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 5(2), Available at <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED501453.pdf>.
- Saunders, M. N. K., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2019). *Research Methods for Business Students* (8th ed.). New York: Pearson Education.
- Venkatesh, V., Morris, M. G., Davis, G. B. & Davis, F. D. (2003). User acceptance of information technology: toward a unified view. *MIS Quarterly*, 27(3), 25-478
- Yomere G. & Agbonifoh A.F. (1999). *Research methodology in social sciences and education*, Benin Uniben Press 19-37.